

Assessing the Research Output of the Botany Department at Visva-Bharati: Insights and Trends

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Abstract: *The author's writing as well as the researchers' diligence, logic, subject, etc. are making it feasible to speed up a conventional experiment. This paper highlights the PhD theses awarded in the Department of Botany of the Visva-Bharati during the period 2010-2020. During these last 10 years, a total of 57 doctoral theses have been approved and awarded. The objective of this paper is to analyse the PhD theses by some parameters to show the trends of Botany research. The bibliographic information that was necessary for the study was taken from the dissertations and theses area of the university. It was discovered that out of 57 PhD theses, the years 2016, 2019, and 2018 had the most contribution. Additionally, it was discovered that the majority of the research tasks were carried out in fields such as genetics, cytology, and microbiology.*

Keywords: *Bibliometric, Citation analysis, Theses, Botany, Content analysis.*

Introduction

Research is a structured approach to investigation designed to uncover, analyze, and refine facts, theories, or practical applications in order to enhance knowledge and comprehension. Productivity is the measure of how efficiently inputs are converted into outputs, often quantified as the ratio of output to input. Research productivity is the output of scholarly work, such as publications or patents, relative to the resources invested, such as time or funding. Bibliometric uses quantitative measures like publication counts, citation indices, and impact factors to assess research productivity and impact. It helps identify trends, evaluate individual and institutional performance, and guide funding and strategic decisions. This study is build up on research activities of the Botany department of Visva-Bharati of West Bengal from 2020 to 2020.

The Department of Botany of Visva-Bharati came into existence with Undergraduate Honors course in 1965 followed by Post graduation introduced in 1967. Presently research works are being carried

out in various frontier areas of plant sciences like genetic diversity of plants and microbes, genomics and metagenomics, stress biology, fungal and algal metabolites, reproductive biology, pollen allergens, ethnobotany, and Orchid conservation. The faculty members have received International and National recognition viz., Alexander Von Humboldt Research Fellowship, Raman Post-Doctoral Fellowship, Visiting Scientist in US universities, Germany and Sweden, INSA Exchange Fellowship etc. The department is recognized by DST-FIST(II) and UGC DRS(SAP-II). Faculty members have research grants from various Govt. agencies like DBT, UGC, CSIR, ICMR, Tea Board, SERB, DST and Govt. of WB etc. The department has consortium of Algal culture. The faculties have international collaborations with Hungry and Welcome trust UK; and National tie-ups with BSI Kolkata, WWF, IIT Rourkela, University of Burdwan (Network project), Tripura University (DBT-NER programme), and Guwahati University.

Review of the Literature

In the context of doctorate research conducted at the Dr. B.A.M. University Library in Aurangabad, bibliometric analysis was performed on a variety of metadata components including language, subject, faculty, and guide, amongst others. According to Veer and Sontakke (2011) bibliometric information has been utilised to both characterise and assess chronological distribution of Ph.D. theses, language and subject wise theses, faculty wise quantum of theses, rank list of guide and guide-wise distribution of theses of Dr. B.A.M. University. From the establishment of this university total 67 Ph.D. degrees was done per year on an average. These were submitted mainly in the discipline of Science followed by Social Science. In 2004, a content analysis work by Thakur and Trikha regarding the post graduate theses in Development Communication field between 1996 to 2001. In this study they showed that majority of research work are on educational technology followed by development journalism. Purposive sampling method is mostly used. In order to analyse the data, the majority of the researchers relied on estimation. Each of the theses had a review presentation that was arranged chronologically, and each thesis included a bibliography that was arranged alphabetically. Between the years 1996 and 2001, a total of 26 post-graduate theses were completed and submitted. A bibliometric analysis of Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University's doctoral theses of subject of Library and Information Science (LIS) was carried out in 2021 by Sonkar, Kushwaha, and Sharma. The study focused on Ph.D. theses. They studied the 28 Ph.D. theses during 1995 to 2018. Another similar work by Pawar and Chandrappa covering thesis of Botany during the period of 1990-2017, awarded by Pt Ravishankar Shukla University. The information that was used in Agricultural Science Ph.D. theses written at Central University of Venezuela between the years 1986 and 2002 was analysed by Chaparro-Martinez and Marzal (2008). Two bibliometric studies have been done by Mishra, Gaude and Solanki (2014) and Singh (2015) on doctoral theses English and LIS respectively. In both the cases year wise submission, sub-divisions of the subjects, reference, guide etc. are used as parameters of analysis. In a survey of the PhD degrees awarded in the field of Library and Information Science of the University of Burdwan on between 1984 to 2015, Mondal and Roy analysed 33 Ph.D. theses against some parameters like year-wise, language-wise and gender-wise productivity of theses, ranking of supervisors, type of references used and their numbers, length of chapters, subject-wise distribution etc. They came to the conclusion that the majority were conducted in the field of bibliometrics studies, knowledge discovery, library rules and regulations, and community services(CIS). Nandi and Kumar reported on the productivity of the Botany subject of the University of Burdwan from 1960 to 2000. They have done bibliometric analysis of 160 (theses) and 739 (articles). Okeji done a bibliometric analysis in the field of LIS in Nigeria from the period of 2000 to March, 2018. Shukla, Goswami and

Sharma reported the result of a bibliometric analysis of 50 Ph.D. theses in Botany of Vikram University, Ujjain from 1991 to 2006. They carry out this study with the intention of tracing the progression of Botany research at the PhD level over the course of the sixteen years. The researchers have decided to focus their attention on the issue of air pollution.

Objectives

The main objectives of the study are written below:

1. To examine the development and patterns of doctoral dissertations in Botany research output in Visva-Bharati of West Bengal.
2. To analyze the patterns and output of academic supervisors.
3. To analyze the subject content on which Botany PhD thesis mostly published.
4. To understand gender-based distribution of Ph.D. dissertations.
5. To point out the supervising pattern of the theses submitted by the research scholar of Botany.

Scope

The study focuses exclusively on research activities related to Botany, drawing on theses submitted to the Central Library of Visva-Bharati and the Indian Thesis Database (Shodhganga). Due to time constraints, the research is limited to theses submitted between 2011 and 2020. Specifically, it examines fifty-seven Ph.D. theses from the Botany department at Visva-Bharati, West Bengal, awarded from 2010 to 2020.

Methodology

This study analyzes the research output of doctoral theses submitted to the Botany Department at Visva-Bharati, West Bengal, from its inception up to 2020. A bibliometric approach was employed for the analysis, with data gathered from two sources: The Indian Thesis and Dissertation Database Shodhganga and the Central Library of Visva-Bharati. PSPP and MS Excel were utilized to apply the bibliometric techniques.

Data Analysis

Data for this study has collected as on said methodology. After collecting data, it has been sorted for purposeful analysis. After that it is superimposed in a single data presentation form to give at a glance scenario of research output.

Table 1 – Showing the Number of Thesis Published on Botany in Visva-Bharati of West Bengal

Sl. No.	Year	No. of Theses	%
1.	2011	2	3.51
2.	2012	7	12.28
3.	2013	3	5.26
4.	2014	5	8.77
5.	2015	4	7.02
6.	2016	12	21.05
7.	2017	3	5.26

Sl. No.	Year	No. of Theses	%
8.	2018	8	14.04
9.	2019	8	14.04
10.	2020	5	8.77
	Total	57	100

Figure 1: Showing the Year-wise Trend of doctoral Thesis on Botany in Visva-Bharati of West Bengal

Table 1 presents a year-by-year breakdown of the 57 Ph.D. theses submitted to the Department of Botany at Visva-Bharati between 2010 and 2020. This table clearly illustrates that the highest number of theses, totaling 12, were submitted in the year 2016, representing 21.05% of the total submissions. This makes 2016 the peak year for the number of doctoral theses submitted within the examined period. The data also highlights variability in submission rates over the years. For instance, in 2011, only two theses were awarded, accounting for just 3.51% of the total submissions. This significant fluctuation indicates differing levels of research output from year to year, with notable peaks and troughs in the number of theses submitted.

Table 2 – Showing the Subject Coverage of Doctoral Thesis on Botany in Visva-Bharati of West Bengal

Sl. No.	Rank	Subjects	No. of Theses	%
1.	II	Cell Biology	9	15.79
2.	V	Embryology	5	8.77
3.	-	Palynology	-	-
4.	VII	Plant Taxonomy	1	1.75

Sl. No.	Rank	Subjects	No. of Theses	%
5.	VI	Plant Physiology	3	5.26
6.	II	Plant Ecology	9	15.79
7.	-	Palaeobotany	-	-
8.	III	Genetics	7	12.28
9.	-	Phytogeography	-	-
10.	VII	Phycology	1	1.75
11.	IV	Mycology	6	10.53
12.	-	Lichenology	-	-
13.	-	Bryology	-	-
14.	VII	Pteridology	1	1.75
15.	I	Microbiology	14	24.56
16.	-	Pomology	-	-
17.	-	Anthology	-	-
18.	-	Agrostology	-	-
19.	-	Dendrochronology	-	-
20.	-	Phenology	-	-
21.	-	Dendrology	-	-
22.	-	Xylotomy	-	-
23.	VII	Morphology	1	1.75

Figure 2: Showing the Subject Coverage of Doctoral Thesis on Botany in Visva-Bharati of West Bengal

Table 2 provides a detailed breakdown of the subject-wise distribution of Ph.D. theses within the Department of Botany. The data reveals that the majority of doctoral research focused on Microbiology, which constitutes 24.56% of the total theses. This is followed by research in Cell Biology and Plant Ecology, each representing 15.79% of the theses. The table also indicates that certain specialized sub-fields, including Palynology, Palaeobotany, Lichenology, Bryology, Pomology, Anthology, Agrostology, Dendrochronology, Phenology, Dendrology, and Xylotomy, have not been explored in the submitted theses. This lack of coverage in these areas suggests that there are significant gaps in the research landscape, highlighting opportunities for future investigation and exploration within these specialized sub-disciplines.

Table 3 – Showing the Contribution of the supervisors in Doctoral Research Output on Botany in Visva-Bharati University of West Bengal

Sl. No.	Rank	Supervisor's Name	No. of Theses
1.	I	Nirmalya Banerjee	9
2.	II	Chowdhury Habibur Rahaman	8
3.	III	Narayan Chandra Mandal	7
4.	III	Subrata Mondal	7
5.	IV	Sudhendu Mandal	6
6.	V	Sukanta K. Sen	5
7.	VI	Kashinath Bhattacharya	4
8.	VI	Samit Ray	4
9.	VII	Bomba Dam	3
10.	VII	Rup Kumar Kar	3
11.	VII	Soma Sukul	3
12.	VII	Swadesh Ranjan Biswas	3
13.	VIII	Jnanendra Rath	2
14.	VIII	P. Lakshminarasimhan	2

Figure 3: Showing the Contribution of the supervisors in Doctoral Research Output on Botany in Visva-Bharati of West Bengal

This study examines a total of 57 Ph.D. theses awarded, guided by over 14 different supervisors, including both individual and joint supervisory arrangements (as detailed in Table 3). Among these supervisors, Prof. Nirmalya Banerjee stands out as the most prolific, having overseen the highest number of theses, with a total of 9, thus securing the top position.

Following closely is Chowdhury Habibur Rahaman, who has supervised 8 theses, placing him in the second position. In third place are Narayan Chandra Mandal and Subrata Mondal, each supervising 7 theses. The table provides a comprehensive list of all supervisors involved, offering a clear overview of their contributions to the Ph.D. research output.

Table 4 – Showing the Gender-wise Contribution of Research Scholars in Doctoral Thesis on Botany in Visva-Bharati of West Bengal

Gender of Research Scholars	No. of Research Scholars	%
Male	32	56.14
Female	25	43.86
Total	57	100

Figure 4: Showing the Gender-wise Contribution of Research Scholars in Doctoral Thesis on Botany in Visva-Bharati of West Bengal

Table 4 provides a detailed breakdown of the gender distribution among doctoral scholars. It shows that there were a total of 32 male scholars, which constitutes 56.14% of the cohort, while 27 female scholars made up 43.86%. This indicates a higher proportion of male scholars compared to female scholars within the sample. Additionally, the table highlights that the year 2016 saw the highest number of scholars, with 12 individuals contributing during that year. This peak in 2016 suggests a notable increase in scholarly activity or productivity within that specific year, in comparison to other years within the examined period. This information offers insights into gender distribution trends and temporal patterns in doctoral research output.

Table 5 – Showing the Guideship Pattern of the Doctoral Thesis on Botany in Visva-Bharati of West Bengal

Supervisor	No. of Theses	%
Single	39	68.42
Joint	18	31.58
Total	57	100

Figure 5: Showing Guideship Pattern of Thesis Published by Botany Department in Visva-Bharati of West Bengal

Table 5 reveals that the majority of doctoral theses, accounting for 68.42%, are overseen by a single supervisor. This indicates that a significant proportion of research work is conducted under the guidance of one primary mentor. In contrast, only 18 theses involve joint supervision, where multiple supervisors collaborate in guiding the research. This data highlights the preference or tendency for individual supervision in the academic environment represented, while also acknowledging the relatively smaller but notable presence of collaborative supervision in the doctoral thesis process.

Major Findings

1. 2016 is regarded as the most prolific year as this year yielded the greatest number of theses, i.e. 12. In 2018 and 2019 the number decreases to 8. In 2011 only 2 theses were published.
2. Among the 14 supervisors, Prof. Nirmalya Banerjee's contribution is notably significant, followed by Chowdhury Habibur Rahaman, Narayan Chandra Mandal and Subrata Mondal's contributions with 8, 7 and 7 numbers of theses respectively.
3. Microbiology, Cell Biology, Plant Ecology, Genetics and Mycology are emerging as the most dominant fields of Botany research in Visva-Bharati of west Bengal.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Botany Department at Visva-Bharati University has achieved a commendable level of research productivity, marking significant contributions to the field of botany. Its scholarly output not only advances botanical sciences but also addresses crucial environmental and ecological challenges. The department's impact is evident through its research in plant genetics, conservation, and sustainability. To build on this success, it is essential for the department to continue fostering innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration. Embracing emerging technologies and integrating

diverse scientific perspectives will be key. Strengthening global partnerships and securing funding for ambitious projects will further enhance its research capabilities. By pursuing these strategic priorities, the department can maintain its leadership role and continue to address pressing global issues effectively.

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